

THE PROBLEM OF FORMING SELF-CONTROL IN STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980840>

Abstract. *The article deals with the main features of training specialists at the University, in particular the formation of students' self-control. The relevance of the topic is caused by the constant increase in the share of independent work and the reduction of classroom work in the curricula of the University. As a consequence, this intensification of training leads to the need to develop self-control skills in the first semesters of training. Self-control is considered as the most important method and stage of independent work of the student in the learning process, necessary both in classroom and extracurricular activities. The novelty of this work is the description and systematization based on the analysis of modern scientific literature on the topic of information on the main aspects of the problem. The definition of "self-control" is given, the levels and methods of its formation are described. Stages of formation of self-control of students are offered and described: from external control to an assessment and control of classmates and, at last, self-control. The necessity of self-control in the process of preparing a student for professional activity is determined.*

Keywords: *self-control, self-esteem, self-improvement, the formation of self-control, the levels of self-control.*

Statement of the problem in general terms and its connection with important scientific and practical problems. In accordance with the requirements of state educational standards of the latest generation, curricula at universities are formed today taking into account a significant proportion of independent work of students. Self-education, self-realization, self-control, self-assessment are the necessary conditions for the successful completion of the educational process [1]. In addition, the direction of professional training at the university becomes practice-oriented and, consequently, the role of students' independent activity increases. The level of self-control becomes the main criterion for the professional competence of a specialist. Without self-control there can be no competence. An important aspect of the student's learning activity is self-control and self-assessment, when learning outcomes are determined and evaluated by the student himself. In addition, unlike the control carried out by the teacher to test knowledge, skills and abilities, self-control should be carried out by the student during the entire process of his learning.

The task of modern higher education institutions is not only to create the basis for the further development of the student, to teach them to make decisions, to develop the ability to independently evaluate themselves, to understand the content of their activities, but also to find ways, methods and means of its implementation for their subsequent transfer to others [3].

Thus, modern higher education should develop students' ability to self-control and self-assessment in any activity.

Formation of the goals of the article. The aim of the work is to consider self-control as the most important method and stage of the student's independent work in the learning process, which is necessary both in classroom and extracurricular activities.

Methods, techniques and technologies used in the study. The authors stand on the positions of a systematic approach and use the dialectical-metaphysical principle. The work describes and systematizes, based on the analysis of modern scientific literature on the topic, data on the main aspects of the problem of self-control. The definition of the concept of "self-control" is given, the levels and methods of its formation are described. The stages of formation of students' self-control are proposed and described: from external control to assessment and control of classmates and, finally, self-control.

Presentation of the main material of the study with a full justification of the obtained scientific results. It is necessary to start developing the skills of self-control and self-assessment of one's activities at the university from the first year of study and perform this work in various types of educational activities and at different stages of the educational process. Purposeful and systematic work on the formation of self-control has a positive effect on the assimilation of knowledge provided by the program, activates creative activity and independence of thinking, which largely determines both the understanding of the program material and the ability of students to regulate themselves and stimulate their professional development.

Also L.M.Alieva and Z.N.Izmailova in the process of self-control is proposed to take into account: "the psychological readiness of students to exercise self-control; the ability to recognize and concretize the ultimate goal; possession of methods of self-examination; possession of self-assessment techniques; ability to analyze deficiencies and determine measures to eliminate them.

Self-control actions that have specific functions occupy a special place in the structure of educational activities in the preparation of specialists at the university: they fix the attitude of students towards themselves as the creator of this activity, as a result of which their attention to solving an educational problem is professional and always aimed at achieving the final result. to which one should aspire. Today, the result of professional training at the university is the professionalism of a university graduate [1].

Taking into account the activities performed by the student for the purpose of self-control, the following levels of self-control formation can be distinguished:

Complete lack of control. The student does not notice and does not correct the errors that occur, in general, he poorly understands the essence of the actions performed. In this case, he is not able to correct the mistake not only himself, but even when the teacher points it out.

Involuntary attention. Control is unconscious and intermittent. The student superficially understood the scheme of actions, controls the execution rather unconsciously [4].

Voluntary attention. The student makes mistakes when performing a new task, but with comments he is able to eliminate errors and explain their causes.

Actual control at the level of voluntary attention. The student follows a clearly conscious pattern. Errors occur very rarely and are often corrected by the student himself during the execution. However, when faced with a non-standard task that requires a different approach, he is helpless and cannot deviate from the previous scheme.

Potential reflexive control. With the help of a teacher, the student regularly and accurately performs standard and non-standard tasks. He controls his actions directly in the course of the task.

During a conversation with a teacher, he confidently defends the results, using scientific methods as arguments.

Actual reflective control. The student can not only control the compliance carried out according to the general template, but also change this template when the task criteria change. Often, he can make these changes before the problem is solved, ahead of the events in his head. The work of the student is carried out at a high level without the help of a teacher.

Dialectical unity of critical and creative thinking. The student can not only control the compliance of the work carried out according to the general template, but can also perceive any information creatively, as well as criticize it. Thanks to creative thinking, new ideas are created, and through critical thinking, their shortcomings are revealed [2].

At the very beginning of teaching self-control, the teacher should familiarize students with the proposed methods for applying self-control in their work. Then you should pay attention to the most

independent analysis and evaluation of the final effective methods and techniques, on the appropriateness of choosing an option in certain cases, on the activity of their application. The development of self-control of students is stimulated by the complex use of a variety of methods and techniques:

“transmission of additional information about the studied material in the form of historical references, facts related to other sciences;

modeling of non-standard situations;

a combination of practical tasks in pedagogy, private methods of psychology, philosophy, sociology, in order to create integrity and logical harmony;

holding student conferences and olympiads;

preparation and presentation of abstracts, reports at seminars;

conducting business games;

acquaintance with art, thanks to which one can develop the ability and desire to replace several concepts with one;

introduction of electronic consultations and manuals into the learning process”.

While studying at the university, students should be able to constantly improve their self-control skills, since the ultimate goal of organizing a self-control system is to transfer this function to students so that self-control is not called a “threat” of pedagogical control, but becomes the norm in the educational process [2].

One of the types of control is mutual control. This is a situation where both communication partners are interested in feedback (teacher - student, student - student). During mutual control, each of the participants in the process can make changes to further work, changing previously used actions with new, more productive ones. Mutual control and control are the foundation for the formation of self-control as a mechanism for self-regulation of a person in a situation of interaction and joint educational and pedagogical activities. The formation of real self-control by the student of their results of opportunities is most effective when they themselves participate with teachers in joint educational and evaluation activities. The process of transition from external forms of control to self-control usually consists of 3 stages:

the leading role of external control, when the criteria for evaluation activities are determined by the teacher.

involvement of students in the independent formulation of evaluation criteria, and then in evaluation work in the conditions of their joint educational activities, when the student performs control and evaluation functions instead of a teacher in relation to his classmates.

mutual control of students becomes the basis for the transition to self-control.

As a result, the skills formed in the student, taking into account the common criteria, norms and requirements known in advance to all participants in the educational process, create an adequate self-esteem, stimulate the growth of trust and mutual understanding of all stakeholders, develop planning skills and coordinated actions, and also contribute to the establishment of friendly and professional relationships with each other and with the teacher.

The purposeful organization of training, the inclusion of self-control, mutual control, control of classmates in the general educational and pedagogical activities contribute to an increase in educational activity and an increase in the progress of students, their motives and professional orientation, the formation of their professionalism and socially significant personality traits.

Research findings. Thus, involving students in self-control and its development makes a positive contribution to the development of the professionalism of future specialists. An important form of manifestation of the activity of the individual in the learning process is self-control, which occupies the main place among the prerequisites for the formation of skills. The ability to control one's own work and, on this basis, to correct it, is one of the manifestations of the independence that students need to acquire, deepen and expand knowledge.

To date, vast experience has been accumulated in studying the psychological foundations of self-control, its physiological nature, pedagogical problems of self-control, the place and role of self-control in the development of students' abilities, opportunities for improving students' self-educational activities, the impact on students' activation, ways to use self-control in the learning process of the program.

The study of psychological and pedagogical literature shows that the problem of self-control over the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities arose along with the need to acquire new skills and knowledge. This problem has not lost its relevance and continues to draw the attention of psychologists and educators.

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